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Interrupted Terms, Frustrated Careers? The Political Continuity of Cabinet Ministers Affected by Presidential Interruptions

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ABSTRACT

This research explores the political fates of Latin American cabinet ministers who served in a government interrupted by crisis. Although the fall of a sitting president means the end of a particular cabinet, the political careers of its members need not perish. Through a classification of career models and C-means cluster analysis, this study considers numerous factors that may influence the political survival of ministers following a crisis at State level. The results indicate differences based on such variables as expertise, party ties, and specialisation, indicating that certain profiles show a greater capacity for remaining in politics. A work methodology is proposed by which to classify career trajectories, and empirical evidence is produced on a topic scarcely explored in the relevant literature, offering new perspectives on political resilience in contexts of instability.

1 | Introduction

The rigidity of term-length or mandate is one feature that distinguishes presidential from parliamentary systems (Linz 1990, 1996; Valenzuela 2004). In a presidential system, the Head of State can be removed from office by only three routes: impeachment, revocation of the mandate, or resignation. Thus the interruption of a presidential term is associated with a context of crisis, with major impacts on both the functioning of the political system and the career of the outgoing president. The instability that has often characterised the Latin American region justifies close examination of this phenomenon, and a significant body of scientific literature has been produced on the fall of Latin American leaders and Heads of State (Pérez-Liñán 2008; Hochstetler and Edwards 2009; Llanos and Marsteintredet 2010; Przeworski 2014) as well as their subsequent trajectories (Siavelis and Morgenstern 2008; Anderson 2010; Cordero and Funk 2011; Alcántara 2012; Alcántara et al. 2016). At the same time, scant

attention has been paid to the cabinet ministers who formed part of failed presidential mandates. Given the novelty of this subject and the lack of background information, an exploratory approach was adopted for the present research.

Although early departure by the head of the executive branch further entails a cessation of activities by the cabinet, this does not necessarily end the political careers of cabinet ministers. Studies such as Camerlo et al. (2025) show that in the case of Argentina, careers remain fluid, and interruptions can lead a former minister to change arena or territorial level.

The excessive personalisation of presidentialism overshadows the role of the cabinet as an executive body, and so little has been written on the ultimate trajectories of cabinet members. In order to contribute to a pertinent discussion and provide new empirical evidence, this study offers a snapshot of the cabinets of presidential systems by highlighting the career paths of outgoing ministers

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after the early termination of their terms. Are they condemned to ostracisation? What characteristics are displayed by those who survive the fall of a Head of State?

To answer these questions in a systematic way, a classification is proposed of political career models, to consider whether any connections exist between the trajectories followed by former ministers and their political survival in the wake of presidential interruption.¹ Based on the definition and operationalisation of career models, this study uses C-means cluster analysis to classify ministers from failed cabinets. Data processing was performed using the MATLAB R24b program, and further study was conducted on the variables of interest selected for ministers who formed part of failed cabinets.

The analysis was conducted in two phases. In the first phase, all ministers who had been part of a president's cabinet were included; next, only those in office at the time of the interruption were selected. For purposes of comparison, the case studies were grouped using this technique, then the after-effects of presidential interruption were characterised for each cluster.

The results show differences among the several career models in terms of political survival, informing the discussion on how variables such as expertise, party ties, or specialisation can shape diverse career types. This research also offers evidence on how career paths can impact the ability to continue in political activity in executive positions in the wake of a crisis such as the interruption of a presidential term.

This study seeks to contribute in two ways. First, it presents a conceptual and methodological proposal for classifying various career profiles. Second, it provides empirical evidence on an aspect little addressed in the specialised literature on presidential interruptions and cabinets: the ability of ministers affected by such interruptions to remain in politics after the mandate ends.

This paper is organised as follows. First, an exploration is made of the contexts and causes of interrupted presidential mandates in Latin America, from the Third Wave of Democratisation (Huntington 1991) to the present day, as a justification for studying the trajectories of ministers from terminated cabinets. Second, a conceptual and methodological proposal is made to identify different career patterns, to test whether patterns can be identified between the type of trajectory followed and the ability to remain in politics after a context of crisis.

2 | Cabinets in Latin America: Stability, Formation Strategies and Member Profiles

2.1 | Stability of Presidential Terms in Latin America (1981–2024)

Since 1981,² more than 20 ruptures have affected fulfilment of the term of office of a Head of State in the democracies of Latin America. Those resignations or dismissals were the result of extraordinary circumstances and mechanisms, including illness, social unrest, judicial declarations of mental incapacity, abandonment of office, impeachment, and *coups d'état*.

To identify the units of analysis, this research employed the PresCab Project database, equipped with a 'selection' variable that collects information on the duration of terms of office, distinguishing four scenarios: (a) regular terms, (b) interrupted terms, (c) interim terms and (d) interrupted interim terms.

Based on the classification of interruptions and interim periods, Figure 1 shows a descending scale of regularity among governments in the Americas; the eight leading democracies that have been most stable are Uruguay, Chile, Costa Rica, Colombia, Panama, Mexico, Nicaragua and El Salvador. In contrast, Bolivia and Ecuador stand out as the least stable countries in the region. As shown in Figure 2, the 1970s marked a turning point in the regularity of presidential terms in the Americas, ushering in a period of growing government stability. This declined in the late 1990s, then recovered (with ups and downs) in the first decade of the 2000s.

In total, in over three decades of democracy in Latin America, 10 countries have been affected by presidential interruptions. Various scenarios can be systematically distinguished to explain presidential interruptions. Some exceptional cases arise from the death or illness of a president (Majluta in the Dominican Republic; Maduro in Venezuela; Banzer/Fernández Quiroga in Bolivia); others arise from questions of electoral malfeasance or lack of 'fair play' (Balaguer in the Dominican Republic; Morales/Áñez in Bolivia), or from the collapse of economic governance (Alfonsín, De la Rúa/Duhalde in Argentina) or from national political intrigues that result in the early departure of the Head of State and an assumption of office by interim leaders (Lugo/Franco, Cubas/González in Paraguay; Rousseff/ Temer in Brazil). Still others derive from subversion of the institutional order (Zelaya/Micheletti in Honduras; Serrano/Espina/deLeón in Guatemala; Fujimori (I) in Peru; Castillo/Boluarte in Peru) or else its refounding (Chávez/Carmona/Cabello in Venezuela). Finally, the criminal involvement of leaders in corruption scandals has led to the early termination of numerous administrations (Pérez/Maldonado in Guatemala; Collor deMello/Franco in Brazil; Pérez/Lepage/Velázquez in Venezuela; Fujimori (II)/Paniagua, Kuczynski/Vizcarra/Merino in Peru; Mahuad/Noboa, Gutiérrez/Palacio in Ecuador).

These data indicate that presidential interruptions have been fairly constant in Latin American politics since the transition to democracy, leading to increased interest by academia. Since the seminal works of Linz (1990, 1996), the literature on presidential interruptions has addressed the conceptualisation (Kim and Bahry 2008), the causes (Mejía and Polga-Hecimovich 2010), and the consequences (Marsteintredet 2008) of this phenomenon, characterised by the early departure of a Head of State without the subsequent collapse of the democratic regime (Pérez-Liñán 2003; Colomer and Negretto 2005; Mainwaring and Scully 2008; Samuels and Hochstetler 2011).

Nevertheless, maintenance of the democratic system does not prevent members of a former president's cabinet from remaining within the system.

H1. *Although presidential downfalls generate turbulence and crises of governance, they do not, in themselves, mean the end of the*

FIGURE 1 | Types of presidential terms.

political careers of ministers. This may indicate that having been part of a presidential cabinet can remain an asset.

This hypothesis responds to the lack of academic literature focusing on the political future of members of the executive branch affected by presidential interruptions. Although numerous studies address the topic of cabinets, looking at the profiles of members (Inacio 2013), or the ways that public trajectories influence the selection of a ministerial cabinet (Camerlo 2013; Camerlo and Pérez-Liñán 2015; Amorim Neto 2000; Rennó and Wojcik 2015), or which variables favour the survival of ministers within the executive branch (Bustamante and Olivares 2016), relatively few studies apply such theoretical frameworks to the concept of ministers removed from office due to a president's forced departure.

2.2 | Strategies for Forming Presidential Cabinets

Academic interest in Latin American presidential cabinets emerged in the late 1990s as a reaction to works by such authors as Arend Lijphart (1990) and Juan Linz (1990), who identified presidentialism as a system that tended towards inter-institutional conflict, discouraged cooperative dynamics and favoured democratic instability.

Based on those concerns, a body of literature has developed addressing the composition of cabinets as a strategic decision made by the president (Valadés 2016). Here the literature argues

that presidents tend to select ministers based on party affiliation, technical knowledge, or personal ties, depending on the context and their political needs. When presidents recruit partisan ministers, they seek to gain control of the legislative agenda.

Thus, although heads of the executive branch in presidential systems do not formally depend on the legislature to be elected or to complete their terms, successful governance is fostered by maintaining a fluid relationship with the parliamentary arena (Camerlo and Mejía 2024). This can also be a resource for controlling an organisation and generating a climate in the party that is favourable to the presidency (Kopecký and Mair 2012).

The selection of independent or non-partisan ministers linked to professional associations or organised groups is fundamentally aimed at finding candidates with technical skills and a positive track record in diverse areas of political action (Inacio 2013). Finally, purely personalistic recruitment strategies from a president's private sphere seek to reinforce loyalties outside the party (Camerlo 2013). In many cases, personal trust can serve as a complement (Gómez and Verge 2012) or even take precedence over technical criteria (Geddes 1994).

The choice of cabinet members responds to the strategic dilemmas of appointment and organisation faced by the president (Barragán 2024). The head of the executive branch can use appointments as a system of rewards for the most loyal members of a

FIGURE 2 | Evolution of the regularity of presidential terms.

party organisation; they can also reward personal loyalties or seek a path to extra-parliamentary agreements, or prioritise technical profiles to deal with crisis situations. Depending on the strategy adopted, the president will consider two individual attributes: loyalty and expertise (Inacio 2013).

2.3 | Career Profiles of Ministers

The concept of a ministerial career is essential to understanding the range of ministerial profiles and the ability to survive a failed cabinet. The notion of ‘career’ can indicate the stages or positions that define the role played by an individual within the political sphere (Rodríguez Teruel 2011). This covers not only the time in office but also the years spent before becoming a minister (Blondel 1991).

The career can be viewed from a linear perspective, where an individual achieves a specific political position, or it may be seen as a succession of positions on a fluid path. Depending on events and opportunities, the arena (or political level) changes, so that new positions of diverse hierarchy (political or non-political) can be occupied. Thus the termination of a specific political role need not mean the end of a professional career; rather, the career is interrupted for a certain time and within a certain level, arena or hierarchy (Camerlo et al. 2025).

Although contextual aspects such as national or party rules may be important, personal characteristics remain relevant to the study of a minister’s political career (Siavelis and Morgenstern 2008).

Given that careers may be interrupted for multiple reasons, a minister’s political survival can be understood as their ability to return to public office (Lunding et al. 2019; Rodríguez Teruel 2011). This capacity for survival depends on their usefulness to the president and whether their accumulated capital is personal, partisan, or technical in type (Barragán 2024). Thus, the design and formation of a cabinet respond (at least in part) to the president’s strategies for gaining support and maintaining governability. Given the importance of a president’s position, they must ensure that the ministers chosen will be able to carry out the government’s interests effectively and efficiently, avoiding erroneous decisions that can mean high costs for the cabinet and rejecting courses of action contrary to the wishes of the head of government (Dowding and Dumont 2015). A president will therefore be aware that great care must be taken in the choice of ministers, so that his or her objectives can be met.

Based on the above, an initial distinction can be made in relation to ministerial career profiles: partisans and non-partisans. The former are dominant in modern democracies; they respond to a

mutual bond between an individual and an organisation that supports and contains its members, under the expectation that the relationship will be long-lasting (Blondel 2005). Partisan profiles are understood as those that carry weight within an organised party structure and that act on behalf of the party (Camerlo and Castaldo 2024), establishing stable links that transcend personal relationships with leaders in power. Their survival is linked to the organisation, which is why they demonstrate greater resilience during crises. So it comes as no surprise that ministers with significant links to their party are more likely to survive should a mandate be interrupted. Based on the above, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H2a. *Ministers with party affiliations show a high rate of continuity in their careers after a president's fall, highlighting the importance of the party as a safeguard.*

Within party profiles, some individuals may belong to a president's circle of trust and prioritise personal over organisational loyalty. Thus, as Olivares and Medina (2020) point out, heads of government may follow purely personal strategies and include close associates in their cabinet. The position of such a minister is based primarily on individual ties; accordingly, they show a high degree of dependency on the president in office.

Some cabinets have room for individuals from outside party organisations, especially in cases where the president has greater independence from the party (Blondel 2005). The introduction of such outsiders into cabinets responds to a search for balance between incentives distributed within the organisation and the need to recruit new cadres with whom to establish direct alliances outside the party sphere (Amorim Neto and Strøm 2006; Tavits 2009).

Among independent profiles, heterogeneity is significant. As Amorim Neto (2000) indicates, the characteristics of independent ministers vary according to the government's objectives; they may be technicians, academics, businesspeople, or actors from civil society. Technocrats tend to predominate among non-partisan ministers, who are seen as possessing rational symbolic resources and political independence (Joignant 2011; Semenova 2020).

Based on the above, the following working hypothesis can be proposed:

H2b. *Ministers with independent profiles will be put in charge of portfolios perceived as complex, to help generate symbolic resources of a rational nature.*

The literature on presidential cabinets has explored the incentives of presidents when appointing members of their teams. However, the extent to which ministers need a particular president and party to remain in politics has been little discussed. This research starts from an assumption that any political system might find very traumatic: the early termination of a presidential term. Against that backdrop, this study considers variables that may affect the political survival of ministers of a fallen president, depending on the type of career pursued: partisan, technical, or trust-based.

As indicated in the previous section, another potential factor is the cause of a presidential interruption, which can affect cabinet ministers in different ways. The underlying causes can impact how a minister is perceived and, consequently, their ability to recover political capital (Marsteintredet 2008; Pérez-Liñán 2003; Llanos and Marsteintredet 2010). Hence, the following research hypothesis is formulated:

H3. *The cause of the presidential interruption is an important factor that could invalidate the significant weight of a career, prompting differences within the group in terms of a minister's capacity for political survival.*

Finally, it should be noted that the timing of a minister's appointment is also relevant. According to Bustamante and Olivares (2016), who studied the case of Chile, ministers in office at the time of an abrupt event face a greater risk of not being reappointed later. Based on that statement, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H4. *Ministers who are in office at the time of the presidential interruption see their continuity in politics as more compromised than those who once formed part of that president's cabinet but were later replaced.*

3 | Methodological Strategy

This study aims to verify whether the interruption of a presidential term implies the end of the political career for that president's cabinet ministers; it also seeks to identify in an exploratory manner any differences in the likelihood of survival among various career patterns. To that end, the trajectories of ministers who formed part of a cabinet affected by a presidential interruption have been reconstructed. Analysis began with a clustering approach, similar to that used in studies by Jäckle (2023) and Lunding et al. (2019). For the development of career categories, a deductive approach was employed that combined various models of party careers. This method of constructing categories was necessary in order to control the effects that each type of career may have in situations where a term of office is interrupted.

The analysis included variable selection, data validation and cleaning, and case classification using clusters. Based on that classification, data were generated according to whether a minister was in office at the time of the presidential interruption, as well as the similar and differentiating characteristics of each group of ministers (Figure 3).

3.1 | Variables and Classification of Career Profiles

Based on the scientific literature discussed in previous sections, this study proposes the operationalisation of the dependent variable based on three types of career models. The first, called the *technical career*, refers to ministers with an eminently technical background (Amorim Neto 2000; Joignant 2011; Semenova 2020). The second model refers to those who build their careers and enter a cabinet primarily through bonds of trust, designated the *trust-based career* (Olivares and Medina 2020; Gómez and

FIGURE 3 | Data analysis procedure. *Source:* The authors.

TABLE 1 | Variables.

	Type	Variable	Parameters	Theoretical justification
Membership in a political party	Categorical	Party affiliation	1. No 2. Yes	Amorim Neto (2000); Blondel (2005); Joignant (2011)
President's party	Categorical	Link to the president	1. No 2. Yes	Samuels and Hochstetler (2011); Gómez and Verge (2012)
Previous terms by appointment	Numerical	Continuity of previous political career	Any number	Dowding and Dumont (2015); Semenova (2020)
Previous terms by election	Numerical	Continuity of previous political career	Any number	
Type of ministry	Categorical	Weight of ministerial portfolio	1. Not determined 2. Reproduction 3. Production 4. Preservation	Siavelis and Morgenstern (2008); Haavio-Mannila and Dahlerup (1985)
Level of education	Categorical	Linked to knowledge expertise	1. Bachelor's 2. Master's 3. PhD 4. Non-university 5. Military career	Rodríguez Teruel (2011)

Source: The authors.

Verge 2012; Geddes 1994). The third model corresponds to those with party affiliation and strong links to the organisation (Blondel 2005; Camerlo and Castaldo 2024); the *party career*.

Although a simple clustering process was carried out with a series of specific variables, these were subsequently supplemented with another series of variables to further explore the main characteristics of the categories generated. To operationalise each of the categories, variables used in the literature on ministerial trajectories were employed; these considered a subject's party affiliation, previous training and experience (based on technical posts, electoral ties, or positions of trust), and their profile in terms of expertise (relating to the type of portfolio held). Table 1 summarises the variables used to construct the career typologies:

In this way, the ministerial career has been considered through variables that seek to define the individual characteristics (party

affiliation, education, membership in the president's party) of each minister, their previous career in appointed or elected positions, and the type of portfolio held. The selected variables were both categorical and numerical. As regards the former, two dichotomous variables were created to verify membership in a political party and whether it was the president's party. To address a minister's type of experience, their level of education³ and the profile associated with the cabinet position they held were both considered, classifying portfolios according to their 'productive', 'reproductive' or 'preservative' nature (Haavio-Mannila and Dahlerup 1985).⁴ Although this sort of classification has been traditionally used in gender studies, to determine the role of women in politics and public decision-making, the importance of this variable lies in the relevance of the various portfolios held by cabinet members. Important factors of whether ministers were selected on the basis of technical expertise, party affiliation or personal trust with the president can show greater propensity

towards specific types of portfolios. A further category of ‘undetermined’ was added for ministries that could not be classified.

In terms of ratio variables, consideration was made of the number of positions previously held, both elected and appointed, taken as necessary variables for understanding political careers and their formation.⁵

Based on these variables and considering the career models discussed in the existing literature on presidential cabinets, Table 2 proposes the following typology:

As explained above, after classifying the cases, observations for each of the above variables were divided according to whether a minister held a cabinet position at the time of the presidential interruption.⁶ Once the clusters were defined, variables related to the timing and type of presidential interruption were cross-referenced to identify intra-group variations (Table 3).

TABLE 2 | Career profiles.

Type of career	Characteristics
Partisan	Ministers affiliated with a party, mostly the president’s party. They have electoral careers, although they may also have held positions of trust. They stand out in ‘preservation’ portfolios due to their importance for the functioning of the cabinet as a whole.
Technical	Ministers who do not have party affiliation. They have a high level of education, with post-graduate studies. In the case of those who have held public office, most have been appointed positions. They generally hold ‘production’ portfolios, which require a more technical profile.
Trusted	Ministers with party affiliation and a history of holding appointed positions. They generally hold ‘production’ or ‘reproduction’ portfolios.

Source: The authors.

TABLE 3 | Variables related to presidential interruption.

Variables	Type	Variable	Parameters	Theoretical justification
Departure due to interruption	Categorical	Departure due to abrupt institutional event	1. No 2. Yes	Valenzuela (2004)
In office during the interruption	Categorical	Occupation of position at the time of departure	1. No 2. Yes	Llanos and Marsteintredet (2010)
Reasons for departure	Categorical	Phenomena that led to the interruption	1. Resignation, economic crisis 2. Resignation, questioning of electoral fair play 3. Resignation, corruption 4. Natural causes 5. Re-founding 6. <i>Coup d’etat</i> 7. Impeachment	

Source: The authors.

In this case, emphasis has been placed on the contextual elements related to tenure in office, the presidential interruption itself, and the causes that prompted it.

3.2 | Data Processing

This work is based on cluster analysis, a statistical technique that allows a homogeneous population (in this case, ministers from Latin American democracies) to be divided into different categories (García-Ferrando and Escobar 2017) (see Appendix A). The idea is to detect patterns of belonging in a number of case studies, in order to recognise other patterns (Bezdek et al. 2019). The data were processed through Matlab R24b, a programming and calculation platform used for data analysis, algorithm development, and model creation. Development of the code was assisted by artificial intelligence, which made refinements and improvements in terms of efficiency. As the selected variables were both quantitative and qualitative, a methodology was chosen based on Fuzzy C-Means (Bezdek et al. 2019), with the categorical variables already normalised through a procedure known as ‘one-hot encoding’ (Géron 2019). The potential of this methodology lies in the fact that calculations based on classical methods do not recognise overlaps in category for diverse cases, whereas the Fuzzy C-Means approach does. The estimation was made considering that membership within a cluster is determined by the distance between the points of the centroids (Velmurugan and Santhanam 2010).

In computer science and other related disciplines, it is common to form clusters containing both qualitative and quantitative data, given that large databases often combine many types of data (Ji et al. 2012). As mentioned previously, the variables were transformed using one-hot encoding, where the categorical variables were divided according to whether they were close to the variable (i.e., whether they were ‘fulfilled’ or not) (Géron 2019). Specifically, these variables were converted into binary numerical vectors, with dimensions equal to the number of categories of the original variable.

To verify the viability of the results obtained, the Fuzzy Partition Coefficient (FPC) was calculated at 0.4178. This indicates

that fuzzy participation was in this case moderate; hence the importance of including other data for analysis at a later stage to verify the hypotheses put forward.

3.3 | Study Universe and Data Availability

Between 1981 and 2024, there were 25 presidential interruptions due to death, illness, resignation, or removal from office (Table 4). From this universe of interrupted terms that took place during the period, the only case excluded was that of President Raúl Cubas and his cabinet, due to the lack of access to data needed to reconstruct the trajectories of the various portfolio holders. Therefore, this research covers almost the entire universe of study, taking into consideration case variations in terms of countries, time periods, and causes of early departure and/or crisis.

The results of this research are based on an original database created by the authors and based on a biographical study of the ministers. The database was constructed using information gathered from institutional websites, the press, and in some cases

consultations with country experts on the subject. As regards the number of cases, an initial database was obtained with 975 observations. This was then reviewed and purged to discard cases without data on political party affiliation, membership in the president's party, previous terms of office by appointment or election, education or type of ministry.

The number of observations was thus reduced to 622; given the large number of missing cases, it was decided to calculate clusters, to classify the observations according to whether the minister was technical, political, or chosen as a personal appointment by the president.

4 | Career Patterns of Ministers in Failed Governments

Figure 4 illustrates the diffuse membership of each of the cases included in the database. The 'fuzzy membership' condition was employed because the formulas used for classification through fuzzy C-means calculate only the probability of belonging to each

TABLE 4 | Case studies.

Country	President	Term length	Number of portfolios	Ministers during term	Ministers at time of interruption
Argentina	Raúl Ricardo Alfonsín	10/12/1983–8/07/1989	8	28	8
Argentina	Fernando de la Rúa	10/12/1999–20/12/2001	13	25	13
Bolivia	Hernán Siles Suazo	10/10/1982–06/08/1985	14	67	14
Bolivia	Hugo Banzer Suárez	06/08/1997–07/08/2001	15	37	15
Bolivia	Gonzalo Sánchez de Lozada (II)	06/08/2002–17/10/2003	16	21	16
Bolivia	Evo Morales Ayma (III)	22/01/2015–10/11/2019	18	34	17
Brazil	Fernando Affonso Collor de Mello	15/03/1990–29/12/1992	15	26	14
Brazil	Dilma Vana Rousseff (II)	1/01/2015–12/05/2016	36	65	30
Ecuador	Jaime Roldós	10/08/1979–24/05/1981	15	25	15
Ecuador	Abdalá Jaime Bucaram	10/08/1996–06/02/1997	20	20	20
Ecuador	Jorge Jamil Mahuad Witt	10/08/1998–21/01/2000	16	27	16
Ecuador	Lucio Edwin Gutiérrez Borbúa	15/01/2003–20/04/2005	16	47	16
Guatemala	Jorge Antonio Serrano Elías	14/01/1991–01/06/1993	14	24	14
Guatemala	Otto Fernando Pérez Molina	14/01/2012–03/09/2015	15	38	15
Honduras	José Manuel Zelaya Rosales	27/01/2006–28/06/2009	30	51	29
Paraguay	Fernando Armindo Lugo Méndez	15/08/2008–22/06/2012	21	39	20
Peru	Alberto Kenya Fujimori (I)	28/07/1990–5/04/1992	13	42	13
Peru	Alberto Kenya Fujimori (II)	28/07/1995–21/11/2000	14	67	14
Peru	Pedro Pablo Kuczynski	28/07/2016–23/03/2018	19	37	19
Peru	Pedro Castillo	28/07/2021–07/12/2022	19	72	19
Dominican Republic	Silvestre Antonio Guzmán Fernández	16/08/1978–05/07/1982	21	23	21
Dominican Republic	Joaquín Antonio Balaguer Ricardo	16/08/1994–16/08/1996	18	23	18
Venezuela	Carlos Andrés Pérez Rodríguez (II)	02/02/1989–21/05/1993	22	61	19
Venezuela	Hugo Chávez	2/02/1999–10/01/2001	15	44	15
Venezuela	Hugo Chávez	10/01/2013–5/03/2013	32	32	32

Source: The authors.

FIGURE 4 | Diffuse membership. *Source:* The authors.

FIGURE 5 | Distribution of observations by cluster. *Source:* The authors.

of the clusters. This does not permit an absolute assignment to be made, but it does allow calculation of the probability of belonging. Nevertheless, while some observations might be said to have ‘fuzzy membership’, the majority (462) exhibited a proportion greater than 0.45 of being assigned to a specific cluster, amounting to 83 cases in the first cluster (55.34%), 130 in the second (62.8%), and 249 in the third (90.54%).

Next, Figure 5 shows the cluster assignment based on the highest probability that the observation is part of the assigned group. Cluster 1 has 150 observations (23.74%), cluster 2 has 207 (32.79%), and cluster 3 has 275 (43.51%).

As concerns the characteristics of the ministers grouped into each cluster, three profiles were identified that essentially fit the conceptual proposal presented in Table 2: supporters, technicians and confidants of the president.

Cluster 1 fits the profile of a party careerist. Practically all observations (97.33%) had a party affiliation, although only 58.7% belonged to their president’s party. In addition, this is the group with the most electoral experience: the average number of elected positions prior to entering the ministry was 2.45. Nevertheless, this was not incompatible with having held appointed positions (average: 2.73). In terms of educational levels, most (60.67%) had bachelor’s degrees but no post-graduate degrees. Of the three groups, this cluster occupies the highest percentage of ‘preservation’ portfolios (39.33%), whereas the percentage of ‘production’ portfolios was similar to the other two groups (at 42.67%), and ‘reproduction’ portfolios amounted to 16%.

Cluster 2 corresponds to technical profiles. This is the group with the highest percentage of ministers with master’s or doctoral degrees (both accounting for about 50% of the total number of observations and 51% of the total cluster). In addition, only

FIGURE 6 | Ministers from a failed cabinet who ended their career due to presidential interruption (aggregate). *Source:* The authors.

FIGURE 7 | Ministers from a failed cabinet who ended their career due to presidential interruption (by cluster). *Source:* The authors.

29.95% had a party affiliation, and none belonged to the president's party. On average, they held 0.16 elected positions before becoming ministers but had more experience in appointed positions (1.66 positions). In terms of the portfolios held, 'production' stood out (44.93%), followed at a distance by 'preservation' (29.95%) and 'reproduction' (25.12%).

Finally, Cluster 3 corresponds to profiles close to the president. Here, all members had a party affiliation and belonged to the president's party. Unlike those in the first group, they had little experience in elected office, having held just 0.14 positions on average. They also exhibited the lowest value (compared to the other groups) in terms of appointed positions (1.01, on average). Therefore, their greatest accumulated capital was their position within their president's circle, with fewer ministers holding master's or doctoral degrees than in Cluster 2. As regards the ministries headed, 44% held portfolios related to 'production', 28.36% to 'reproduction', and 27.27% to 'preservation'.

5 | Which Ministers Survive A Presidential Interruption?

Once the different career profiles were conceptualised and the observations grouped into clusters, Hypothesis 1 was verified.

Figure 6 shows in aggregate terms the number of ministers who remained in politics after a presidential interruption. The results indicate a high rate of permanence in politics: 528 of the 632 ministers studied (83.5% of the observations) continued to hold public office after the fall of their president. In contrast, only 104 (16.5%) politicians ended their political careers.

To identify differences between groups and to test Hypotheses 2a and 2b, Figure 7 shows how the observations grouped in Cluster 1 (corresponding to ministers with partisan profiles) were those that exhibited the greatest continuity in politics following the presidential interruption (88.67%). This was followed by trust-based profiles (82.91%) and technical profiles (80.68%).

Figures 6 and 7 provide an overview of the effects of presidential interruptions on all ministers who were, at some point, part of the cabinet of a president whose term was cut short.⁷ Later, in order to refine the analysis, attention was focused solely on ministers in office at the time of the president's fall. This allowed verification of Hypothesis 3.

Departures from politics are not uncommon in situations of presidential interruption (Cordero and Funk 2011). Furthermore, the continuity observed between the different clusters is quite even,

FIGURE 8 | Ministers in office who ended their career due to presidential interruption (aggregate). *Source:* The authors.

FIGURE 9 | Ministers in office who ended their career due to presidential interruption (by cluster). *Source:* The authors.

indicating that all career profiles showed a similar proportion of ministers leaving the government. This suggests that other variables, such as institutional and contextual factors, can have an impact on individual careers (Siavelis and Morgenstern 2008). However, the party profile cluster had a much smaller impact on departure than the rest, indicating that party affiliation can open new opportunities for ministers who have suffered interruptions (Camerlo and Castaldo 2024). This contrasts with profiles based more heavily on trust, where political capital arises from personal dealings with the president. Similarly, technical profiles showed a lower survival rate, attributable to a minister's loss of reputation as a result of their departure.

Figure 8 shows that, although most ministers remained in politics whether in office during an interruption or not, a substantial difference is observed between the two groups. Although only 7.20% of those who belonged to a cabinet before a president's fall saw their careers interrupted, 27.72% of those who were in office at the time of the failed mandate did not

return to public office. This discrepancy reinforces the idea that elements related to those institutions and events that led to a presidential interruption are indeed relevant (Bustamante and Olivares 2016).

When comparing the political longevity of ministers who were in office at the time of an interruption, segmented by cluster, the results follow the trend shown in Figure 8. Ministers with a party background showed the highest survival rate, followed by ministers trusted by the president and those with a technical profile (see Figure 9). However, this again confirms a higher rate of departure from politics compared to ministers who left a cabinet before the interruption. In addition, members with a technical profile were more affected by an interruption, in proportional terms, than the other two groups.

Finally, this study aims to verify whether a correlation exists between the cause of presidential interruption and the ability to remain in politics (Figure 10a–c).⁸ Here ministers with a partisan profile showed greater capacity for political survival when a

FIGURE 10 | (a–c) Cause of presidential interruption and ability to remain in politics (by cluster and whether the exit was due to interruption). *Source:* The authors.

presidential interruption was due to impeachment. Conversely, they were more likely to leave public life when the departure was due to corruption. Notably, in the case of technocratic ministers, impeachment was the main cause for ending their political careers. Finally, ministers trusted by the president, such as party members, were punished for corruption cases above all else.

6 | Conclusions

This study contributes to research on the trajectories of members of presidential cabinets affected by extreme crises, such as (in this

case) an early interruption of their term of office. This is particularly relevant in the Latin American region, given the numerous presidential downfalls since the advent of the third wave of democratisation.

The results show that presidential interruption does not mean the end of a minister's political career, thus confirming Hypothesis 1. This suggests that the political system is capable of creating alternatives for this group, and it points to the resistance of ruling elites in positions of power.

In general terms, (Hypotheses 2a and 2b) and the relationship between the different profiles in terms of survival indicate notable differences among the categories. Ministers with backgrounds linked to party politics have shown higher survival rates following a crisis due to the role of their party as a buffer. On the other side of the coin are technical profiles, which have tended to exhibit a lower survival rate thanks to their limited penetration into party institutions. Halfway between these two are trust-based profiles, the fate of which has been more closely linked to a president's career. Thus the results show that the independent status of technical experts is more harmful to a future political career than maintaining a close relationship with a failed president—which fails to confirm Hypothesis 2b.

It was also found that the causes of interruption affect each profile differently. The partisan profile is more affected by corruption, whereas the position of trust is more affected by the abrupt removal of a president through legal mechanisms or by force. Finally, impeachment affects the technical profile most, indicating some component of trust linked to the results of the legislature. This finding reinforces the idea that crises can affect ministers differently, and that de-legitimisation takes different forms depending on the circumstances of a crisis. Based on the above, Hypothesis 3 is confirmed.

The study further finds a greater probability of leaving politics for ministers who held office during an interruption. Overall, this research contributes to explaining ministerial careers within turbulent contexts in the Latin American democracies. The analysis undertaken emphasises the notion that a political career is not made invalid by crisis events, but rather that the context and profile contribute to shaping a former minister's fate.

This exploratory work represents an initial discussion on the interruption of ministerial careers. Future development of this subject could include comparisons among profiles, the incorporation of new variables, and statistical treatment based on the use of regressions and differential equations. Moreover, future research could generate a collection of longitudinal studies on each of the countries studied, to achieve more homogeneous results for each country.

Data Availability Statement

Research data are not shared.

Endnotes

¹ Those who held cabinet positions at some point during a president's term but were later replaced by another were excluded.

² The year 1981 was taken as the starting point because it marks the first interruption of a presidential term in Latin American democracy. This corresponds to the death of Ecuadorian President Jaime Roldós.

- ³ The degree program or original profession was not included, because a larger number of variables generates a higher level of partitioning, which increases diffusion within the model.
- ⁴ To observe the distribution of observations, refer to Tables A1–A4 in the Annex.
- ⁵ See Figure A1 in the appendix.
- ⁶ See Figure A2 in the appendix.
- ⁷ To see the distribution of ministers in office at the time of interruption, refer to Figure A2 in the appendix.
- ⁸ See Tables A5 and A6 in the appendix.

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Appendix A

Formulas Used for Cluster Formation

Considering the methodology, the following calculations were performed:

- $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N\}$, in which data from N points are combined. Each of these points is composed of normalised numerical and categorical variables encoded numerically using one-hot encoding.
- $C = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_K\}$ is the set of centroids, with K clusters.
- $U = [u_{ij}]$ is the fuzzy membership matrix with dimensions $N \times K$, where each value u_{ij} represents the membership of point x_i to cluster j when the following is true:

$$\sum_{j=1}^K u_{ij} = 1, \quad \forall i$$

In addition, m was set as the standard diffusion parameter at 2.

Categorical variables were coded considering that a categorical variable A with K possible categories ($A = \{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_k\}$), the vector resulting from the coding is as follows:

$$X_i^{one-hot} = [x_{i1}, x_{i2}, \dots, x_{ik}]$$

For each observation x_i of variable X , the encoding vector for each component of x_{ij} is:

$$x_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if the category of point } i \text{ is equal to } j \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

This generates a matrix in which each row represents an observation and each column represents a specific category.

Subsequently, the fuzzy membership matrix (U) was initialised by performing a normalised random initialisation by rows.

$$u_{ij}^{(0)} = \frac{rand()}{\sum_{j=1}^K rand()}, \quad \forall i, j$$

Next, the centroids (c_j) are calculated through iterative updating, using averages weighted by high fuzzy membership m .

$$c_j = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (u_{ij})^m \cdot x_i}{\sum_{i=1}^N (u_{ij})^m}, \quad \forall j$$

In this sense, x_i is the combined vector (numerical + coded categorical) of point i and $(u_{ij})^m$ is the membership of point x_i to cluster j , raised to parameter m .

Each value u_{ij} is updated using the Euclidean distance between point x_i and centroid c_j :

$$u_{ij} = \frac{1/d_{ij}^2}{\sum_{k=1}^K (1/d_{ik}^2)}, \quad \forall i, j$$

By adding the Euclidean distance, the resulting formula is

$$d_{ij} = \|x_i - c_j\| = \sqrt{\sum_{l=1}^P (x_{il} - c_{jl})^2}$$

where P is the total number of combined variables, x_{il} is the value of point i in variable l , and c_{jl} is the value of centroid j in variable l . In the case of distance, $d_{ij} = 0$, it is replaced by a minimum value (ϵ) to avoid a division by zero.

The calculations are completed using the maximum absolute change between the centroids in consecutive interactions so that it is less than the tolerance (tol) as follows:

$$\max_j (\|c_j^{(t)} - c_j^{(t-1)}\|) < tol$$

Finally, each point x_i is assigned based on the highest fuzzy membership to one of the clusters.

$$cluster(x_i) = \arg \max_j (u_{ij}), \quad \forall i$$

The model was verified using the Fuzzy Partition Coefficient (FPC):

$$FPC = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^K (u_{ij})^2$$

TABLE A1 | Party affiliation of cabinet ministers (by cluster).

Cluster	No political outlet due to interruption						Political exit due to interruption						Grand total
	No party affiliation		Party affiliation		Total		No party affiliation		Party affiliation		Total		
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	
Cluster 1 (supporters)	4	3.01%	129	96.99%	133	100.00%	0	0%	17	100%	17	100%	150
Cluster 2 (technocrats)	110	70.05%	57	29.95%	167	100.00%	35	87.50%	5	12.50%	40	100%	207
Cluster 3 (trustworthy)	0	0.00%	228	100.00%	228	100.00%	0	0%	47	100%	47	100%	275
Grand total	114		414		528		35		69		104		632

Source: Authors.

TABLE A2 | Party affiliation of the president of the ministers who make up the cabinet (by cluster).

Cluster	No political outlet due to interruption						Political exit due to interruption						Grand total
	Not the president's party		President's party		Total		Not the president's party		President's party		Total		
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	
Cluster 1 (supporters)	34	41.46%	48	58.54%	82	100%	28	41.18%	40	58.82%	68	100%	150
Cluster 2 (technocrats)	111	100%	0	0%	111	100%	96	100%	0	0%	96	100%	207
Cluster 3 (trustworthy)	0	0%	154	100%	154	100%	0	0%	121	100%	121	100%	275
Grand total		145		202		347		124		161		285	632

Source: Authors.

FIGURE A1 | Average and nature of positions held (by cluster). Source: Authors.

TABLE A3 | Educational attainment of cabinet ministers (by cluster).

Cluster	No political outlet due to interruption												Political exit due to interruption																			
	Bachelor's degree				Master's degree				Non-university studies				Military career				Bachelor's degree				Master's degree				Non-university studies				Military career			
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Cluster 1 (supporters)	80	60.15%	22	16.54%	21	15.79%	7	5.26%	3	2.26%	133	100.00%	11	64.71%	1	5.88%	3	17.65%	2	11.76%	0	0.00%	17	100.00%								
Cluster 2 (technocrats)	62	37.13%	48	28.74%	45	26.95%	7	4.19%	5	2.99%	167	100.00%	15	37.50%	3	7.50%	10	25.00%	5	12.50%	7	17.50%	40	100.00%								
Cluster 3 (trustworthy)	107	46.93%	56	24.56%	40	17.54%	4	1.75%	21	9.21%	228	100.00%	27	57.45%	14	29.79%	3	6.38%	1	2.13%	2	4.26%	47	100.00%								
Grand Total	249		126		106		18		29		528		53		18		16		8		9		104									

Source: Authors.

TABLE A4 | Type of portfolio held by cabinet ministers (by cluster).

Cluster	No political outlet due to interruption												Political exit due to interruption																											
	Undetermined				Reproduction				Production				Preservation				Total				Undetermined				Reproduction				Production				Preservation				Total			
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%				
Cluster 1 (supporters)	3	2.26%	22	16.54%	56	42.11%	52	39.10%	133	100.00%	0	0%	2	11.76%	8	47.06%	7	41.18%	17	100%	150																			
Cluster 2 (technocrats)	0	0.00%	38	22.75%	81	48.50%	48	28.74%	167	100.00%	0	0%	14	35.00%	12	30.00%	14	35.00%	40	100%	207																			
Cluster 3 (trustworthy)	1	0.44%	62	27.19%	100	43.86%	65	28.51%	228	100.00%	0	0%	16	34.04%	21	44.68%	10	21.28%	47	100%	275																			
Grand total	4		122		237		165		528		0		32		41		31		104		632																			

Source: Authors.

FIGURE A2 | In office at the time of interruption by cluster. *Source:* Authors.

TABLE A5 | Ability to remain in politics depending on different circumstances (by cluster).

Cluster	No political outlet due to interruption							Total
	Resignation due to economic crisis	Resignation questioning of electoral fair play	Resignation due to corruption	Natural causes	Re-founding	Coup d'état	Impeachment/political manoeuvring	
Cluster 1 (supporters)	24.06%	5.26%	22.56%	0.00%	3.01%	4.51%	40.60%	100.00%
Cluster 2 (technocrats)	13.60%	18.42%	15.35%	1.32%	7.46%	25.44%	18.42%	100.00%
Cluster 3 (trustworthy)	23.40%	10.64%	36.17%	0.00%	0.00%	19.15%	10.64%	100.00%

Source: Authors.

TABLE A6 | Presidential interruption based on different cases (by cluster).

Cluster	Political exit due to interruption							Total
	Resignation due to economic crisis	Resignation questioning of electoral fair play	Resignation due to corruption	Natural causes	Re-founding	Coup d'état	Impeachment/political manoeuvring	
Cluster 1 (supporters)	17.65%	5.88%	64.71%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	11.76%	100.00%
Cluster 2 (technocrats)	17.50%	0.00%	25.00%	0.00%	0.00%	5.00%	52.50%	100.00%
Cluster 3 (trustworthy)	23.40%	10.64%	36.17%	0.00%	0.00%	19.15%	10.64%	100.00%

Source: Authors.